

LEVERAGING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR THE PRESERVATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF EGGON INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE

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Abstract: *Indigenous Knowledge (IK) is a vital cultural asset for sustainable development, yet it faces erosion from globalization and cultural shifts. This study examines the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in preserving and developing Eggon Indigenous Knowledge (IK) in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Using a descriptive survey design and a multistage sampling approach, data were gathered from 133 respondents across five Eggon communities. Findings reveal that even though spiritual beliefs, oral traditions, and craftsmanship remain vital, IK documentation is limited. Challenges such as low digital literacy, poor internet access, and risks of cultural misrepresentation hinder AI application were identified by respondents. The study recommends culturally sensitive AI tools, improved documentation, and youth engagement to safeguard Eggon IK and ensuring its sustainability and contribution to global heritage.*

Introduction

All over the world, indigenous knowledge (IK) has been recognized as a valuable resource for addressing various challenges, such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and poverty (IPCC, 2019). The United Nations has emphasized the importance of IK in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UN, 2020). Despite its significance, IK is often marginalized and under-documented,

particularly in rural communities (Taylor, Kukutai, Nakata & Byrne, 2017).

Indigenous knowledge (IK) refers to the unique, traditional knowledge and practices of indigenous peoples, developed over centuries through their relationship with the environment (UNESCO, 2017). Indigenous knowledge in the Eggon ethnic group encompasses various aspects of life, including agriculture, medicine, conservation, and cultural practices. It is a vital

Samuel Otsonu Aboh and Enenche Henry Okoh

component of a community's cultural heritage and plays a significant role in sustainable development. Many of this indigenous knowledge are getting eroded gradually especially with the advent of newer knowledge and technologies. These knowledge if not properly safe guide will be lost out. It is therefore important that this IK are preserved for the next generation for sanctity and identity preservation. To do this, emerging technologies such as data base creation use, documentation and the use of Artificial Intelligence can be deployed.

The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in developing indigenous knowledge has the potential to enhance the preservation and transmission of traditional knowledge. AI-powered systems can analyze and interpret large datasets of indigenous knowledge, providing insights into traditional practices and their applications (Litvinenko, Väättänen, Koppinen & Mäkinen, 2020). Additionally, AI can facilitate the development of digital platforms for documenting and sharing IK, making it more accessible to community members and other stakeholders.

The study is necessitated by the need to preserve and promote indigenous knowledge in the Eggon community, recognizing its significance in achieving sustainable development among this people and world wide. The use of AI in developing indigenous knowledge has the potential to enhance the preservation and transmission of traditional knowledge. Currently, knowledge is proliferated

with the emergence and use of AI technology and the indigenous knowledge of the Eggon people and by extension other indigenous tribes should be preserved for posterity.

Statement of the Problem

The Eggon tribe in Nasarawa State, Nigeria, is facing a significant threat to its indigenous knowledge (IK) due to cultural erosion, urbanization, and climate change. The lack of documentation and limited access to technology have resulted in the loss of traditional practices, customs, and beliefs. Furthermore, the knowledge gap between the older and younger generations is widening, as the younger generation is not learning the traditional practices and customs. This situation poses a significant challenge, as the loss of indigenous knowledge can lead to the erosion of the Eggon community's cultural identity, traditional practices, and customs.

Many of these indigenous knowledge are getting eroded gradually especially and if not properly safe guided, it will be lost entirely as have been experienced with many indigenous knowledge. It is therefore important that this IK are preserved for the next generation for sanctity and identity preservation. To do this, emerging technologies such as data base creation use, documentation and the use of Artificial Intelligence have shown to be of valuable importance when properly deployed.

Additionally, there is a dearth of literature on the use of AI for documentation and preservation of indigenous knowledge in Eggon ethnic group of Nasarawa state, Nigeria. It is not

Samuel Otsonu Aboh and Enenche Henry Okoh

clear if adequate research has been carried out in this area as literature are scarce. These gaps spurred this research on the study for proper harnessing, preservation and use of IK. The rationale for this study is to fill the gap in knowledge by researching on Leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) for the Preservation and Development of Eggon Indigenous Knowledge.

Objective of the study

The main objective of the study is to leverage on AI for the preservation and development of Eggon Indigenous knowledge. Specifically the study looked at three objectives:

- i. To determine the current state of indigenous Knowledge (IK) among the Eggon ethnic communities.
- ii. To identify the components of indigenous knowledge of the Eggon tribe.
- iii. Investigate the challenges associated with AI in generating Eggon indigenous knowledge.

Research Questions

Three research question were asked in the process of conducting this study

- i. What is the current state of indigenous knowledge (IK) Among the Eggon ethnic communities?
- ii. What are the key components and elements of indigenous knowledge specific to the Eggon tribe?
- iii. What are the limitations associated with using AI to generate and preserve Eggon indigenous knowledge?

Review of Relevant Litreature

Concept on the state of Indigenous

Knowledge among Eggon ethnic group

Indigenous knowledge (IK) refers to the unique, traditional knowledge systems and practices developed by indigenous communities through long-standing interactions with their environment (UNESCO, 2019). The IK faces significant threats from urbanization, globalization, and the decline of traditional practices (Abba & Musa, 2019). Interestingly, climate change disrupts the ecosystems underpinning cultural and traditional knowledge use for activities such as agricultural and medicinal knowledge, jeopardizing sustainable practices (Okoronkwo, Abdullahi, & Usman, 2024).

Among the Eggon ethnic group, IK forms the bedrock of cultural identity, expressed through agricultural techniques, traditional healing, spiritual beliefs, and sustainable resource management (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019). As primarily agrarian people, the Eggon cultivate crops such as millet, guinea corn, and yams, showcasing deep ecological insight gained through generations of observation and adaptation (Aboki, 2023). Their skills also encompass hunting, gathering, and craftsmanship, including intricate wood carvings and pottery, which are vital to their cultural and economic fabric (Leadership Nigeria, 2021).

The Eggon's spiritual worldview, centered on Ahogben, the supreme creator, and mediated by Ashim, a deity closer to human affairs, profoundly influences their cultural practices, including the Eggon Festival, which celebrates

Samuel Otsonu Aboh and Enenche Henry Okoh

the farming cycle. Traditional institutions like the Ombatse, despite being controversial and banned, continue to shape community governance, underscoring the enduring relevance of Eggon IK as posited by Aboki, (2023). This knowledge system is holistic, weaving together social, environmental, and spiritual elements, and is primarily transmitted orally through the Eggon language, a Benue-Congo language (Berkes, 2018). However, this oral tradition renders IK susceptible to erosion, especially as younger generations embrace external cultural influences and the Eggon language faces endangerment (Ethnologue, 2025). Preserving Eggon IK is critical not only for maintaining cultural heritage but also for its contributions to global sustainability, aligning with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations, 2020). Understanding the depth and value of Eggon IK is essential for developing AI systems that honor and support their cultural legacy while addressing these challenges.

Concept of the Use of Artificial Intelligence on Indigenous Knowledge

Artificial Intelligence (AI) holds functional potential for preserving and promoting knowledge and especially indigenous knowledge (IK), particularly in the Eggon community, where traditional knowledge faces significant threats (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019). AI technologies, including natural language processing (NLP), speech recognition, and machine learning, can document, analyze, and revitalize IK, ensuring its accessibility for future

generations (Taylor, Kukutai, Nakata, & Byrne, 2017). A primary application is language preservation, as the Eggon language, spoken by a population of over 200,000 people, is at risk due to declining use among youth (Ethnologue, 2025). AI-powered tools can transcribe oral histories, translate texts, and develop language learning platforms, preserving linguistic diversity (The Guardian Nigeria, 2019). For instance, OBTranslate, a Nigerian AI platform, aims to translate over 2,000 African languages (The Guardian Nigeria, 2019). Studies on digital preservation in Nigeria, such as at Ramat Library, University of Maiduguri, demonstrate how AI-driven databases enhance IK accessibility while maintaining cultural integrity (Okoronkwo, Abdullahi, & Usman, 2024). AI can also facilitate education by generating culturally relevant materials, such as interactive apps teaching culturally accepted agricultural techniques or spiritual practices (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019). Additionally, AI-driven decision-making systems can integrate IK into environmental management, supporting sustainable practices aligned with indigenous values (Berkes, 2018). This initiative offering a model for Eggon language revitalization Beyond language, AI supports cultural heritage preservation by digitizing artifacts, music, and traditional practices, creating accessible digital archives.

However, deploying AI in IK preservation presents challenges, including the risk of cultural appropriation, where external entities may exploit or misrepresent knowledge

Samuel Otsonu Aboh and Enenche Henry Okoh

(Litvinenko et al., 2020). Cultural homogenization is another concern, as AI systems may prioritize dominant languages or perspectives, marginalizing intended language (Eggon) and culture (Taylor, Kukutai, Nakata, & Byrne, 2017). Ethical considerations, such as data sovereignty and intellectual property rights, are paramount to ensure community control over their IK. Partnerships, like those that existed between Covenant University and OBTranslate, exemplify community-driven AI initiatives that could be adapted for leverage in cultural communities (Covenant University, 2023). By addressing these challenges, AI can become a powerful tool for preserving and promoting IK in this cause Eggon indigenous knowledge.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research design was used to gather data for this study. Descriptive survey research is crucial for studying effective marketing strategies for promoting academic libraries because it provides valuable insights into the current practices, challenges, and user needs (Okeke-Uzodike, 2022).

The research was conducted in three three (5) Eggon communities of Nasarawa State, located in North-Central Nigeria. Nasarawa State. The state is bordered by Kaduna State to the north, Abuja (Federal Capital Territory) to the west, Kogi and Benue States to the south, and Taraba and Plateau States to the east. The Eggon people are a prominent ethnic group, are renowned for their rich cultural heritage, encompassing traditional farming, spiritual practices. The

study focuses on key settlements namely Akwanga, Lafia, and Wamba selected for their cultural significance and the presence keepers of cultural values where IK is actively practiced and transmitted across generations.

The population of this study is made up of diverse stakeholders in the Eggon communities, including traditional knowledge holders, community elders, cultural practitioners, educators, and young learners, who collectively represent the custodians and beneficiaries of IK. The total population size is six hundred and fifty-four (654) individuals, a manageable yet representative group that ensures depth and breadth in data collection.

A multi level sampling technique was adopted at various levels in this study to select study unit for this research. Using the Taro Yamene sampling technique a sample size of one hundred and thirty-three (133) was selected as respondents for this work. This is aimed at ensuring that the sample is a good representation of the study population.

Questionnaire was the instrument for data collection for the study. The questionnaire used was a research developed instrument. The questionnaire adopted a four (4) point Likert-scale model to gather necessary data. The instrument is designed in line with the research questions and objectives. Data for this study was collected in a community-centered approach to ensure cooperation and ethical engagement. Data collected were collated and analyzed using simple percentage and presented in simple table for easy understanding. The

items with percentage of 100-50 are accepted while those with the percentage 0-40 are rejected.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The data collected for this study were analyzed using simple percentages and presented in tables for easy understanding. The total number of questionnaires administered was one

hundred and forty to prevent the lost of data during collection. They were all duly completed and returned for analysis. One out of the questionnaires returned was found not to be useful and hence was not used for this analysis. The results of the study are presented in accordance with the research questions.

Question 1: What is the current state of indigenous knowledge (IK) among the Eggon ethnic communities?

No.	Item	SA	A	D	SD
1	Eggon Indigenous Knowledge is documented in AI	2.5	10.08	59.7	27.7
2	Eggon youth actively use the Eggon language for cultural knowledge.	50.4	29.4	2.5	17.65
3	Eggon spiritual beliefs remain central to community identity.	60	27.73	2.52	10.1
4	Eggon traditional governance supports indigenous knowledge preservation.	60	27.73	2.52	10.1
5	Eggon indigenous knowledge is threatened by cultural erosion.	53	27.73	9.24	10.1

Table 1

Table above is respond on the current state of indigenous knowledge (IK) among the Eggon ethnic communities. The response showed that 59.7 % of respondents disagreed that Eggon Indigenous Knowledge is documented in AI while 27.7% agreed. 10.5% strongly dis agreed and 2.5% strongly agreed. 50.4 % of respondents strongly agreed that Eggon youth

actively use the Eggon language for cultural

knowledge and 29.4 % agreed.2.5% of respondents disagreed with this and 17.65% strongly disagreed. Response shows that 60 % of the respondents strongly agreed that Eggon spiritual beliefs remain central to community identity 27.7% agreed. While 2.5 % and 10 % disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively.

Samuel Otsonu Aboh and Enenche Henry Okoh

60 % and 27.7% strongly agreed and agreed that Eggon traditional governance supports indigenous knowledge preservation while 9.3% and 6.0% strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively. On the item of Eggon indigenous knowledge been threatened by cultural erosion, 53 % and 27.73% of respondents strongly agreed and agreed while 9.24% and 10.1% respectively, strongly disagreed and disagreed to the

assertion. This implies that currently the cultural practices are affecting indigenous knowledge (IK) among the Eggon ethnic communities.

Question 2: What are the key components of indigenous knowledge among Eggon communities?

No.	Statement	SA	A	D	SD
1	Eggon farming practices show deep ecological knowledge.	3	12	71	33
2	Eggon traditional medicine is widely used in the community.	3	21	60	35
3	Eggon Festival integrates spiritual and cultural practices.	71	33	3	12
4	Eggon craftsmanship is a key part of cultural heritage.	71	33	3	12
5	Eggon oral traditions are the main way to share knowledge.	71	33	3	12

Table 2

Data on table 2 is response to the question on what are the key components of indigenous knowledge specific to the Eggon tribe? 3% of respondents strongly agreed that Eggon farming practices show deep ecological knowledge and 12 %, agreed, while 71% and 33 %, strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively. 60% and 35 % strongly disagreed and disagreed that Eggon traditional medicine is widely used in the community with 3% and 21% strongly agreed and agreed respectively. On the use Eggon Festival integrates spiritual and cultural

practices, 71% and 33% strongly agreed and

agreed to this with 3% and 12% disagreed and strongly disagreed. 71% strongly agreed that Eggon craftsmanship is a key part of cultural heritage and 33% agreed while 3% disagreed and 12% strongly disagreed. 71% of respondents strongly agreed that Eggon oral traditions are the main way to share knowledge and 33% agreed. 12% disagreed and 3 percent strongly disagreed.

Samuel Otsonu Aboh and Enenche Henry Okoh

Question 5: What are the challenges associated with using AI to generate and preserve Eggon indigenous knowledge?

No.	Statement	SA	A	D	SD
1	Low digital literacy limits AI use in Eggon communities.	61	51	4	3
2	Risks AI misrepresenting Eggon cultural knowledge.	61	51	4	3
3	Poor internet access hinders AI tool use in Eggon areas.	81	23	3	12
4	Data sovereignty concerns reduce trust in AI systems.	101	13	3	2
5	Eggon elder collaboration reduces AI ethical challenges.	81	33	3	2
		71	33	3	12

Table 3

Table 5 reports the response on the challenges and limitations associated with using AI to generate and preserve Eggon indigenous knowledge. 61% of respondents responded that they strongly agreed and 51% that they agreed that Low digital literacy limits AI use in Eggon communities while 4% and 3% of respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. On the item of Risks AI misrepresenting Eggon cultural knowledge, the response was same as above. 71% of respondents strongly agreed that risks AI misrepresenting Eggon cultural knowledge a challenge and limitations associated with using AI to generate and preserve Eggon indigenous knowledge and 33% strongly agreed while 3% and 12% disagreed and strongly disagreed. 81% and 23% of respondents strongly agreed and agreed that Poor internet access hinders AI tool

use in Eggon areas is a challenge in the use of AI

in collecting and documenting Eggon indigenous knowledge while 3% and 12% respectively disagreed and strongly disagreed.

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the finding of this study, the following are brought out;

- i. The current state of cultural practices affecting documentation of indigenous knowledge (IK) among the Eggon ethnic communities include; No documentation of Eggon Indigenous Knowledge AI platforms. Youths are not actively using Eggon language for development of knowledge. Another cultural practice currently affecting the documentation of Eggon Language by AI is Eggon spiritual belief which remain central to community identity and

traditional governance system which did not support preservation of indigenous knowledge.

- ii. Key components of indigenous knowledge in the Eggon tribe are farming practices with deep ecological knowledge, traditional medicine is widely used in the community, Festival in the communities integrates spiritual and cultural practices. Additionally, craftsmanship is a key part of cultural heritage and oral traditions are the main way to share knowledge.
- iii. There are various challenges associated with using AI to generate and preserve Eggon indigenous knowledge. This challenges include, low digital literacy limits AI use in Eggon communities fear of the risks AI misrepresenting Eggon cultural knowledge. There is also poor internet access which hinders use of AI tool in Eggon area. Another challenge is the issue of data integrity. There is concern about Data sovereignty which reduces trust in AI systems.

Conclusion

This study investigated leveraging of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered system for developing and preserving Indigenous Knowledge (IK) among the Eggon ethnic community of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Indigenous knowledge among the Eggon people includes farming techniques, spiritual practices, traditional medicine, craftsmanship, oral traditions, and festivals, which are central to their cultural identity but are increasingly threatened by

cultural erosion, urbanization, climate change, and poor documentation.

Nevertheless, challenges remain, including low digital literacy, poor internet access, risks of cultural misrepresentation, and concerns about data integrity. The study recommended culturally sensitive AI development, greater documentation of Eggon traditions, active youth involvement, advocacy for IK preservation, and the creation of community-driven AI databases. This study used the descriptive survey method and multi-sampling was used to draw the subject of the study.

5.4 Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made

- i. Efforts should be made to improve documentation of Eggon culture to help support in its integration into AI platforms.
- ii. Culturally sensitive AI tools should be developed to be used in documenting Eggon people's indigenous knowledge.
- iii. Eggon youths should be engaged in the preservation and documentation of their indigenous knowledge

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